

LEGAL ISSUES OF FORMATION OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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Abstract. A joint-stock company (JSC) is a business company (corporation), the authorized capital of which is divided into a certain number of shares giving their holders the right to redeem, receive dividends and determine the economic policy of the company, make decisions on the appointment of directors, bear burden of related risks. Therefore, the particular aim of this research is to present ways of forming joint-stock companies.

Keywords: government, company, joint-stock, to form, ways, law, legal.

In the modern world, the issues of corporate governance of joint-stock companies with state participation have acquired applied significance. Until now, in the management of joint-stock companies with public participation, there are systemic problems in management and an insufficient level of corporate control. As a result, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Joint Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights" was adopted [1].

One of the ways to improve the efficiency of corporate governance in joint-stock companies with state participation is the formation of an essentially different model of corporate governance, which lies in the fact that the "burden" on the issue of decision-making regarding the management of a joint-stock company is transferred from the federal executive authorities to the collective body of a joint-stock company (board of directors, supervisory board, etc.), whose role is not limited to the execution of "directives" of the state [4].

The collective body in this case is called upon to perform the functions of strategic management, and, accordingly, must be empowered to make decisions, exercise control over the executive bodies of joint-stock companies, and must also bear real responsibility for their actions (inaction).

The reason for the growth of the public sector in the country's economy is the opinion that has been formed for a long time about the ability of the state to ensure the protection of public interests in the sphere of the country's economic pre will not be able to ensure the proper order of this industry, but iocesses. It should be assumed that the participation of the statt will at least be able to balance public and private interests [2, 67-70].

The problems I am considering relate to the expediency and effectiveness of state participation in joint-stock companies, the legislation governing state participation in joint-stock companies and the forms of such participation,

"golden shares" as an instrument of state influence on the management of a company, as well as the process of exercising the rights of a shareholder by the state.

Depending on who is the founder (state / private individuals and legal entities), legal entities are divided into private, public, and mixed [5, 45-50]. Legal entities, the sole founder of which is the state, include state corporations, unitary enterprises, state companies, institutions and joint-stock companies with 100% state participation.

It should also be noted the stages of the establishment of a new joint-stock company, which include: the development of an economic justification for the company being created. As V. A. Galanova notes, from an economic point of view, the foundation should first of all "invent a business." That is, the founders must have an understanding of the future activities of the joint-stock company, its expected profitability, place in the market, advantages over other market participants, t-stock company, consisting of concluding a memorandum of associatioetc ,[3, 86-88].

Then comes the stage of organizing a joinn; holding a meeting of founders; formation of the authorized capital of the joint-stock company and state registration of the formed joint-stock company.

Thus, several types of creation of joint-stock companies with public participation can be distinguished:

- Formation of a new joint-stock company with public participation;
- Transformation of a unitary enterprise into a joint-stock company;
- Introduction of property, which is on the right of state or municipal property, as a contribution to the authorized capital of a joint-stock company (participation in an additional issue);
- Acquisition of shares of joint-stock companies by a public entity.

Conclusion. Summarizing the given data, it can be concluded that the formation of a joint stock company should include the future activities of the joint-stock company, its expected profitability, place in the market, advantages over other market participants. In this way, it will have a bright future.

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